

INVESTIGATION OF KINK-BAND FORMATION UNDER BIAXIAL STRESS STATE

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SUMMARY

This paper investigates longitudinal compressive failure. Two failure modes were observed experimentally for pure longitudinal compression: shear-driven fibre compressive failure and kink-band formation. In a micromechanical numerical study, failure envelopes for combined longitudinal compression and in-plane shear were predicted.

Keywords: kink-band, compression failure, fracture, micromechanics, FEA

INTRODUCTION

Longitudinal compressive strength of carbon epoxy composites is lower than their tensile strength—this constitutes a significant limitation in design. Furthermore, experimental data related to compression typically show a large amount of scatter, which makes their interpretation difficult. To improve the predictions made by physically-based failure models used in design, the failure mechanisms present in compression need to be fully identified and understood.

Carbon/epoxy systems loaded in longitudinal compression commonly fail by kink-band formation [1]. However, other failure mechanisms such as shear failure of the fibres have been observed in M-40 / epoxy [2] and in AS4/1034 [3], or splitting when large in-plane shear stresses are combined with the longitudinal compression [4, 5].

Obtaining experimental evidence of the failure mechanisms has proven challenging due to the difficulty in observing specimens at the microscale while keeping them under load [6]. The present work investigates the failure mechanisms found in longitudinal compression of single edge notch crossply specimens.

In studies investigating the in-plane shear / longitudinal compression case [4, 5, 7], it is difficult to infer a universal trend for the shape of the failure envelope because of the large scatter found in the experimental data.

Finite Element (FE) micromechanical models have been used in the literature [8, 9] to study the effect of different parameters on the longitudinal compressive strength. These models offer the advantage to identify parametric trends which are difficult to infer in the experimental results due to the observed scatter. However, the inputs to the model need to be carefully chosen for the outputs to be meaningful. In the present work, a micromechanical FE model, which allows for the types of failure mechanisms observed

in the experiments to be correctly represented, is used to predict longitudinal compression/in-plane shear failure envelopes.

EXPERIMENTS

Procedure

In previous work [6], detailed observation of kink-band development in unidirectional laminates was restricted by out-of-plane displacements. To reduce this effect, crossply ($90_2,0_8,(90,0)_5$)_S specimens were tested in addition to unidirectional ones.

Figs. 1(a) and (b) show the testing rig and the geometry used for the specimens. The notches were manufactured by using first a band saw (~ 2 mm), then a pre-crack was made with a model saw (~ 0.2 mm) and sharpened with a razor blade (~ 0.1 mm).

The procedure was the same for both types of specimens: (i) a specimen was set into a rig specifically developed for this purpose; (ii) a compressive load was applied until failure was observable on the outer plies; (iii) the specimen was kept under load in the rig and polished to reveal the 0° plies; (iv) the failure process in the 0° plies was observed under an optical microscope.

Figure 1 (a) Micro testing rig; (b) Single edge notch specimen geometry (dimensions in mm).

Results

In crossply specimens, failure initiates at the notch tip, first in the form of fibre shear failures at an angle $\beta \sim 45^\circ$, followed by a region of transition and the formation of a kink-band, as seen in Fig. 2.

In Fig. 2 label (1), the fibres below the faces of the shear crack are slightly bent. During the transition, the upper edge of the failing band is defined by a sharp crack which appears to be the prolongation of the shear failure while the bottom edge appears to be defined by the failure in bending of the fibres. After the transition region, a kink-band propagates at an angle $\beta \sim 23^\circ$.

Figure 2 Fracture in crossply specimens.

In unidirectional laminates, the exact sequence of events (shown in Fig. 3) is difficult to infer in a post mortem examination, but the failure process involves the same mechanisms as the ones found in the crossply specimens. Shear failure of the fibres initiates at the notch and propagates at an angle $\sim 45^\circ$ (label (1) Fig. 3), through approximately 20 fibres. Several failure processes take place at the crack tip (label (2) and corresponding zoom in Fig. 3). Fibres next to the crack tip are rotated over a length of 3 to 5 fibre diameters, label (3). The first fibre at the tip shows a shear failure at $\sim +45^\circ$, label (3), and a second crack lower at $\sim -31^\circ$, the next two fibres only show a crack at $\sim -31^\circ$. However, and on the contrary to the failure process in the crossply, no kink-band develops, and instead the fibre/matrix splits, label (4). It can be seen in Fig. 3 that an in-plane kink-band, label (5), and an out-of-plane kink-band, label (6), appear to be connected to the splits originating from the notch tip, label (7), and the shear crack tip, label (4).

Figure 3 Fracture in unidirectional specimens.

Discussion

From both types of specimens, it appears that failure initiates by compressive shear failure of the fibres at the notch tip. In this region, shear failure is promoted by the large compressive stresses with small rotation of the fibres. As shear failure propagates, the faces of the shear crack slide on each other creating some bending of the fibres ahead of the crack tip, which promotes kink-band formation.

Similar observations were made by Crasto and Kim [3] in unidirectional AS4-epoxy composites axially compressed in an un-notched mini-sandwich setup. They observed that compressive shear failure of the fibres initiate at the edge of the specimen—where the in-plane shear stress τ_{xy} is zero because of the free edge—and, after some propagation, the failure mechanism changes to kink-band formation.

This similarity also suggests that the failure process should be fairly notch insensitive. In the present case, the radius of the notch is sharp (~ 0.05 mm) while Crasto and Kim [3] describe identical sequence of events in un-notched unidirectional specimens.

Figs. 2 and 3 show similar failure processes; however, in the unidirectional case, the shear crack propagates over a shorter distance. It is believed that the presence of the 90° plies can delay the splitting of the fibre/matrix interface but also constrains the rotation of the fibres and postpones the transition to kink-band formation.

MICROMECHANICAL FE MODEL

Model development

The FE micromechanical model shown in Fig. 4 is used to investigate numerically the failure mechanisms found in longitudinal compression and to relate the findings to the experimental investigation presented previously.

The model represents a unit-cell of the composite, with a layer of matrix sandwiched between two half fibres (the fibre diameter is $7\ \mu\text{m}$). The FE model is sheared and compressed. Shearing forces are applied on the right and left edges. A compressive displacement is applied on the right edge of the model, while the left hand side is restricted in the 1-direction. For the compression step, the Riks algorithm is used such that potential snap-back or snap-through can be captured.

Figure 4 FE model.

A nonlinear elasto-plastic behaviour is used for the matrix. The nonlinear shear curve for the matrix is back-calculated from the nonlinear shear curve for the composite (given in [10]) and as shown in Fig. 5. When the effect of the behaviour of the matrix on the failure envelope is investigated, an elastic perfectly-plastic model is used, see Fig. 5. A fracture energy-based damage model implemented in ABAQUS is used for the

fibres, with only fibre tensile and compressive modes activated. The maximum stress criterion is used to predict failure onset.

Finally, periodic boundary conditions are applied on each side of the fibres, so that it represents an infinite array.

Figure 5 Composite shear curves.

Results

The results presented here are compared with experimental results given in Soden et al. [7] in the form of failure envelopes for the case of in-plane shear and longitudinal compression. The experimental data from [7], the predictions from the LaRC05 fibre kinking criterion [11] (used with the inputs given in [10]) as well as the predictions using the present FE model with the nonlinear elasto-plastic and perfectly plastic matrix behaviour, are presented in Fig. 6.

The failure envelope can be divided into two regions (see Fig. 6): region I, where the compressive strength is slightly affected by shear stresses so that the failure envelope runs nearly parallel to the τ_{12} -axis, and region II, where the compressive strength decreases linearly with increasing shear stresses.

The compressive strength is defined as the peak load reached during the compression step. The input value for the fracture toughness of the fibres was not found to influence the peak load. The effect of the length of the model on the failure envelope was also investigated, and as shown in Fig. 7, it did not affect the predictions.

With the data given in [10], the FE model does not capture the longitudinal compressive strength and falls below experimental data for $\tau_{12} > 80$ MPa. However, the general trend—the compressive strength is slightly reduced by shear stresses up to 60 MPa (region I), then decreases linearly with the shear stress (region II)—seems to be captured. The LaRC05 fibre kinking criterion appears to be conservative when used with the inputs provided in [10], but is in good agreement with region II of the FE model, for an initial misalignment angle $\phi_0 = 0.49^\circ$.

Figure 6 Failure envelope.

In Soden et al. [7], it is mentioned that the bi-axial results were obtained from different sets of tubes (two for torsion/compression and one for torsion/tension and pure torsion). Because results in compression are sensitive to material variability, experimental set-up and coupon manufacture, it appears reasonable to look at the different sets independently.

Table 1. Inputs parameter used in the FE model for Figs. 6, 7, 8.

Compressive strength of the fibres X_c^f (MPa)	2000	Used in Fig. 6
	1330	Used in Fig. 7
	1099	Used in Fig. 8
In-plane shear strength S_{12} (MPa)	80	Used in Fig. 6, with nonlinear elasto-plastic behaviour
	125	Used in Fig. 7, with elastic perfectly plastic behaviour
	95	Used in Fig. 8, with elastic perfectly plastic behaviour
Initial misalignment ϕ_0	0°	Used in Fig. 6
	1.5°	Used in Fig. 7
	0.5°	Used in Fig. 8

In Fig. 7, the inputs of the FE model were changed according to Table 1 and so that the apparent higher shear strength of 125 MPa, found in the first set of bi-axial tests, could be reached (an elastic perfectly-plastic model was used for the matrix); the compressive strength of the fibres was decreased to 1330 MPa, so that the longitudinal compressive strength of the composite was reached and the initial misalignment angle of 1.5° was chosen to capture the slope of the linearly decreasing part of the failure envelope.

In region II of the failure envelope in Fig. 7, the trend predicted by the FE model agrees well with the experimental results and with the LaRC05 criterion when used with an initial misalignment angle $\phi_0 = 2.45^\circ$. The agreement between experimental and FE results is also good in region I.

Figure 7 Failure envelope, set 1.

In Fig. 8, the inputs of the FE model were changed according to Table 1 and so that the apparent shear strength of 95 MPa, found in the second set of bi-axial tests, could be reached (an elastic perfectly plastic model was used for the matrix); the compressive strength of the fibres was decreased to 1099 MPa, so that the longitudinal compressive strength of the composite was reached and the initial misalignment angle of 0.5° was chosen to capture the slope of the linearly decreasing part of the failure envelope.

In region II of the failure envelope in Fig. 8, the trend predicted by the FE model agrees well with the experimental results and with the LaRC05 criterion when used with an initial misalignment angle $\phi_0 = 0.55^\circ$. The agreement between experimental and FE results is also good in region I.

Figure 8 Failure envelope, set 2.

Discussion

The main objective of this micromechanical FE study was to investigate numerically the failure mechanisms in longitudinal compression and to relate the findings to the experimental investigation presented in the first part.

The FE models highlighted the fact that two failure mechanisms take place, dividing the failure envelope in two distinct regions. Fibre failures define region I of the failure envelope, where the compressive strength is slightly affected by shear stresses so that the failure envelope runs nearly parallel to the τ_{12} -axis. The location of this region on the σ_1 -axis is directly determined by the compressive strength of the fibres. The value of the compressive strength of the T300 fibres given in [10] is of 2000 MPa and leads to over-prediction of the longitudinal compressive strength of the composite, as seen in figure 6. However, Oya and Johnson [12] reported values of 1000 MPa and 1800 MPa for the compressive strength of T300 fibres, the differences arise when the recoil or direct test method (respectively) is used. In Figs. 7 and 8, values of 1330 MPa and 1099 MPa were respectively used, which are in the range given by Oya and Johnson [12].

Region II of the failure envelope is related to failure of the matrix, leading to kink-band formation and eventually splitting. The shear strength of the matrix is important as it controls the in-plane shear strength of the composite. The shape of the failure envelope in region II is related to the type of behavior used to model the matrix. For an elastic perfectly-plastic behavior, the compressive strength decreases linearly with the shear stress, while the curve becomes concave when the matrix behaviour is changed to nonlinear elasto-plastic (the amount of concavity can be related to the amount of nonlinearity). The slope of the curve is controlled by the amount of initial misalignment. For a given in-plane shear strength of the composite, the curve rotates around the point $(0, S_L)$ when the angle is changed. For large enough misalignment, the curve can cross

the σ_1 -axis before intersecting the portion of the failure envelope defined by fibre failure. The features described for region II of the failure envelope are also captured by the LaRC05 fibre kinking criterion as seen in Figs. 6, 7, 8.

CONCLUSION

An experimental investigation on compression of single edge notched unidirectional and crossply specimens has revealed that failure initiates first at the notch tip by compressive shear failure of the fibres. The misalignment created ahead of the crack tip by the sliding of the crack faces on top of each other leads to kink-band formation. The 90° plies were found to inhibit splitting and to constrain fibre rotation and so result in postponing the transition to kink-band formation.

A micromechanical finite element study showed that the general trend of the failure envelopes presented in [7] could be captured if both compressive shear failure of the fibres and fibre kinking were accounted for.

Further work is under way to numerically investigate the state of stress at the crack tip in the experiments and eventually to relate it to the numerical failure envelope predictions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The funding of this research from the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council and the Ministry of Defence under the project EP/E0Z3169/1 is gratefully acknowledged.

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